

3D printed biodegradable shape memory polymer stimulated both electrically and magnetically

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ABSTRACT

Shape memory polymers (SMPs) are smart materials that can memorize temporary shape and revert to their permanent shape by exposure to an external stimulus such as heat, electric, or magnetic field. SMPs have potential wide applications in aerospace and medical devices^[1], due to its high recoverable strain, controllable mechanical properties and transition temperature, easy processing. Much work so far has focused on polycaprolactone (PCL) as biodegradable shape memory polymer with simple structure induced by heat stimulus^[2]. The electric and magnetic field induced shape change has distinct advantages for effective and fast local heating without environment temperature change^[3]. So using 3D printing and nanoparticles to achieve complex structure with electric and magnetic stimulus is essential for more applications in biomedical area, such as stents.

In our works, we prepared PCL/Fe₃O₄/CNTs shape memory composites with complex structure by 3D printing. Surface modified Fe₃O₄ and CNTs nanoparticles were uniformly dispersed in PCL matrix by melt blending. We successfully achieved fast recovery rate (30s) under low voltage (15 V direct current), and the sample can also be remotely controlled in alternating magnetic field. Thermodynamic properties of PCL/Fe₃O₄/CNTs nanocomposites were studied by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC, TA Instruments Q2000, U.S.A.) and Dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA, TA Instruments Q800, U.S.A.). The electric conductivity were studied by Keithley 4200. Fig 1 shows several photos taken by every 10 seconds in recovery process. We can also see that the sample has high recovery ratio. It must be mentioned that with contents of CNTs increase, the storage modulus above transition temperature increase about 100 times to 10MPa (see fig 2a), but have no influence on melting temperature (see fig 2b). Fig 2c shows conductivity increase to 30 S/m from 5 S/m, which is important for temperature increase induced by electric stimulus.

In conclusion, PCL/Fe₃O₄/CNTs shape memory composites shows high recovery rate and ratio under low voltage and alternating magnetic field. This system could potentially be applied as biomedical devices through 3D printing.

Fig 1 Recovery process of PCL/Fe₃O₄/CNTs shape memory composites under 15 V direct current.

Fig 2 Properties of PCL/Fe₃O₄/CNTs with different contents of CNTs: (a) storage modulus, (b) melting temperature, and (c) electric conductivity

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